

Moneygraphs: Visualizing America's pastime

Sam Bell & Jay Shankar

E-mail: samuel.bell@iu.edu, jshankar@iu.edu

Abstract

This project involves visualizing various aspects of the sport of baseball, with a focus on team building and the business of baseball. The goal was to analyse different types of baseball statistics and determine what makes a players and teams successful. To accomplish this, we developed a method for displaying a longitudinal view of a player's career, incorporating both a player's quality and quantity-based statistics, as well as a player's salary. We determined that it is overall not a good strategy for teams to spend a lot of money on payroll, and to focus on developing cost-controlled players.

1. Introduction

Baseball is one of the most popular sports, not only in the USA, but also Latin America, Asia, and worldwide. Its annual revenues have exceeded 8 billion dollars. It is a big business, and there's a lot of money at stake.

1.1 Team valuation and revenue

Figure 1: Team valuations in \$billions

According to Forbes, the most valuable team is the New York Yankees, worth about four billion dollars. After that, the next most valuable are the Boston Red Sox, Chicago Cubs, Los Angeles Dodgers, and San Francisco Giants. The least valuable team, the Rays, are worth an estimated \$900 million. Most teams are closer to the lower end of the valuation, and there is a large gulf between the five most valuable teams and everyone else.

Figure 2: Attendance by team

If we look at attendance by team, the same five valuable teams are near the top of the list, in addition to a few others: the St. Louis Cardinals (SLN) and the Los Angeles Angels (LAA). The boxplot shows many outliers, and there's a variety of explanations for them. For example, San Francisco (SFN) has two low points; those were the 1998 and 1999 seasons, before their new ballpark opened in 2000. The high points for Texas (TEX) and the New York Mets (NYN) are when their new stadiums opened.

Stadium size also factors into this. Even though Boston (BOS) sells out every game, their average is a bit lower than the others, due to Fenway Park being one of the smallest in baseball. On the other side, Colorado (COL) has two of the highest outliers, due to playing in cavernous Mile High Stadium for two seasons.

Figure 3: Payroll by team

This is a visualization of team payrolls, and once again it's the most valuable teams spending the most money. There are many interesting things to note on this chart. We used a boxplot to make ranges and outliers visible. The Dodgers (LAN) have a few outliers at the upper level, after a new ownership group bought the team in 2012 and drastically increased payroll. Also we can see different philosophies on how to manage spending over the years; compare the steady Braves (ATL) with the boom-and-bust Tigers (DET).

1.2 Payroll vs on-field success

It turns out that there isn't a direct relationship between revenue and success on the field. If we plot team revenue vs team wins for 2017, and look to the top of the chart, we can see four of the five high-revenue teams (LAN, NYA, CHN, BOS), but also four middle-of-the-pack teams (CLE, HOU, WAS, ARI). San Francisco (SFN), the fifth high-revenue team, finished at the bottom.

Figure 4: Revenue vs wins, 2017

There are a few reasons for this. One is that beyond a certain point, teams don't add additional payroll, and just pocket the extra revenue. In fact, aside from the five high-revenue teams, there's no correlation between revenue and payroll at all:

Figure 5: Payroll vs Revenue

Another reason is that even high payroll itself doesn't directly translate to success on the field. We built a plot that shows team payroll by year vs success on the field. The size of the circle indicates wins, and an orange star indicates winning the World Series.

Figure 6: Payroll vs on-field success

Two things become apparent if you look at this chart. One is that payrolls have exploded in recent years, especially after about the 2000 season. We will examine the causes and ramifications of that explosion later.

The other is that the successful teams – the large circles and orange stars – can occur anywhere in the stack. There isn't a smooth gradation downward with a star at the top and then increasingly small circles to the bottom. The star is often in the middle, particularly 2015 (Kansas City), 2005 (Chicago White Sox), and 2003 (Florida). Only once in the past 15 years, the 2009 Yankees, has the top payroll team won the World Series.

Not only is it possible to win with a lower payroll, it's possible to turn a bad team around quickly, with smart drafting and player acquisition. To visualize this, we graphed the standings year-over-year to make comparisons.

Figure 7: Change in NL Central standings

This is the National League Central from 2009-2017. The Chicago Cubs were a last-place team from 2011 to 2014, but after that, were able to make a quick turnaround to become World Series champions in 2016. A similar thing happened in the American League West division.

Figure 8: Change in AL West standings

The Houston Astros were the worst team in baseball as recently as 2013, but became champions four years later. Houston is medium-sized in terms of payroll, attendance, and team value, so how did they do it? How can teams without the deep pockets of the richest teams compete? This is something that we wanted to explore with this project.

2. Review of existing works

Before getting started on this project, we researched the different types of visualizations that are already out there so we could get a sense of what was possible. Baseball is a popular sport, and we were able to find many different ideas.

Possibly the most common and primitive type of baseball visualization is made by fans during the game — the humble baseball scorecard:

Figure 9: A scorecard (baseballscorecard.com)

Without even reading the scorecard carefully, it's easy to see what happened in this game, an 8-2 Tigers win. Each filled-in diamond represents a run. Reading across the rows, it's easy to see what each player accomplished during the game.

2.1 Larger media outlets

Baseball graphics are commonly seen in major media outlets, such as newspapers, TV, and corporate websites like ESPN. Here's an exaple from the New York Times:

Figure 10: Map of baseball fandom (NY Times)

This is a map of the location of the fans of each baseball team. They pulled the data from Facebook by ZIP code. This map is interesting in that it gives you a sense of the geographic reach of the teams in a easy-to-understand way. You can see that the Braves own the entire Deep South, for example, or that the Giants own all of northern California, including the entire Bay Area. (The version on the NY Times website is zoomable; the Oakland Athletics are not even the most

popular team in the area around their own stadium:)

Figure 11: A's are second to Giants in the East Bay? (NY Times)

The main criticism we had of the map was the use of colors. They used alpha to indicate the depth of popularity in different places, which is fine, but that limited their color palette and made it difficult to differentiate certain teams. Where, for example, does Cardinals fandom end and Rangers fandom begin? What are those mysterious red splotches in Utah, North Carolina, and Florida? Why are some areas darker gray than others? The answers to the latter two questions, "Red Sox" and "Yankees", point to a deeper truth that is not readily apparent from the map: those two teams are by far the most popular teams nationally, and at least one of the two shows up as at least third-most popular almost anywhere on the map.

Interestingly, the Washington Post took this map one step further by adding politics:

The partisanship of baseball fans

2014 fan data from Facebook (via the New York Times) overlaid with 2016 support by county.

Figure 12: Baseball political map (Washington Post)

This chart is a bit difficult to read; there's no easy way to see who the most Democratic or Republican fan base is due to the fact that partisanship is expressed as variable-sized non-aligned pie charts. Nevertheless we found it interesting.

Baseball visualization often takes on the form of on-screen graphics displayed during a baseball telecast. This is a commonplace example, the "score bug" displayed on-screen, usually in the corner.

Figure 13: Score Bug (NBC Sports)

The purpose of the bug is to give an immediate visual update of the progress of the game. The yellow diamonds indicate which bases have runners on them. Each network has their own variation of the bug; some display the number of strikes, balls, and outs as little dots instead of numbers.

As computer graphics technology improves, television producers have gotten more creative with their on-screen visualizations. Here's an example, FoxTrax:

Figure 14: FoxTrax (Fox Sports)

FoxTrax shows the locations of all of the pitches that the pitcher has thrown in the at-bat, with numbers to indicate sequence and different shapes and colors to differentiate different pitch types. Opinions on this seem to be mixed; while it is good information, some fans find it distracting and hard to follow without context.

The largest sports-media website is ESPN.com, and they will sometimes publish baseball "infographics". They generally aren't very good. Here is an example of one, about retired numbers:

Figure 15: Retired number "infographic" (espn.com)

As you can see, there is a lot going on here. This graphic combines several different chart types:

- The top area uses symbols to indicate how many players, coaches, and executives have retired numbers. It's difficult to compare these numbers, however because the axis isn't aligned, and the players loop over several rows. Also there's nothing to indicate who's who (maybe put numbers and/or team colors on the symbols?)
- The middle section has a big 42 to tell you that every team retired #42, an area showing teams that retired the same number for multiple players, a wordcloud indicating players with #20 retired, and a section for players with numbers retired for multiple teams. This seems like random bits of information with no real attempt to organize it.
- The bottom section has histograms showing the counts of numbers retired for each team, in order of when the team was established. Maybe they were trying to illustrate that older teams retired more numbers. Unfortunately they didn't scale the years (1901, 1901, 1901, 1961?) so the effect is muddled.

2.2 Community and educational projects

Due to the widespread popularity of baseball, and the wide availability of data sets, the internet community has developed

many baseball visualizations. Here are some examples of visualizations we found from the community.

Figure 16: 2018 AL East race ()

Several websites display graphs like this. This is a pennant race chart. The vertical axis is games above or below 500. This is the 2018 AL East; we can see the Red Sox and Yankees being close until June, and then the Red Sox pulling away. At the bottom, we can see that the Orioles were a disaster.

This is another one we found, from an academic paper:

Figure 17: Eras of baseball

We liked how you could clearly see the different eras of the game due to the use of coloring, and a single, well-chosen statistic. In this case, the vertical axis is the home run leaders for each year. You can easily see Babe Ruth in the 1920s, Mantle vs Maris in 1961, and Bonds and McGwire in the steroid era.

For pure baseball statistics, Baseballreference.com is most people's go-to resource. While the site is built around delivering raw statistics, there are a few visualizations available.

Figure 18: Sparkline displaying team results (baseballreference.com)

There are two main types of pages on Baseballreference.com: Team pages, and player pages. This is a detail of a visualization on a team page; it is a sparkline of the

team's win/loss results. The size of the bar indicates the margin of victory, and the color (redundantly) indicates wins and losses. We liked it because it's easy to understand, and hovering over any bar gives the opponent and score. Drawbacks were that we wish it showed more detail, and we didn't think it was necessary to show the margin in such an exaggerate way. (Margin of victory doesn't matter much in baseball. A win is a win and a loss is a loss. The sparkline makes it seem as if losing by a lot is more important than losing by a little, but that isn't really true.)

Figure 19: Player page (baseballreference.com)

This is an example of a player page. The top has a photo of the player, some "badges" indicating the player's most important accomplishments, and a display of their uniform numbers. The main section of a player page, however, is just a series of big, spreadsheet-esque grids of numbers.

Figure 20: Grid of baseball stats (baseballreference.com)

Although this is fairly dry, they did take a few steps to make the data more visually engaging. Stars next to the year indicate all-star appearances. Numbers in boldface are league-leaders, and numbers highlighted in gold at the bottom are all-time records. In this example, Rickey Henderson is baseball's all-time leader in Runs, Stolen Bases, and Caught Stealing.

One site we found that was a treasure trove of interesting baseball visualizations is Craig Robinson's Flip Flop Fly Ball (<http://www.flipflopflyin.com/flipflopflyball/>). Here's an example of one of the many innovative charts on the site:

Figure 21: Postseason schedule (Flip Flop Fly Ball)

This chart shows how baseball's postseason keeps getting later in the year. The vertical axis is years, and the horizontal axis is days; the purpose of this chart is to illustrate that the World Series starts much later than it used to. Notice the annotations for special cases, like World War I, September 11, or the 1989 Bay Area earthquake.

Figure 22: World Series winners vs best record (Flip Flop Fly Ball)

Figure 26: Pitching correlation chart

Figure 28: Offensive statistics

3.3 Player statistics

So, which players should a team get? To answer this question, a team should look carefully at a player's statistics. For offensive players, it's important to find players who can hit for average and power, and drive in runs.

Figure 27: Median salary

Figure 29: Correlations of offensive stats

If we look at what the market pays for, the offensive stat with the strongest correlation to salary is runs batted in. Most of the players fall between 60 – 100 RBI. Although home runs does not have the strongest correlation to salary, notice that all the three offensive stats are positively correlated to salary, indicating that players who perform well in the long term tend to be highly paid.

Figure 30: RBI vs salary

The clear outlier on the scatterplot is Alex Rodriguez of the Yankees, who was making over \$25 million per year.

Regular Season %Wins Vs Payroll (1998-2015)

Figure 32: Regular Season Win% vs payroll

Figure 31: Defensive Stats

On the defensive stats, we see that ERA has slightly negative correlation with salary which is better for pitchers. In fact, their salaries are determined by their ability to win games. So did the salaries really matter for the team performance ?

To investigate this we analysed the impact of payroll on regular seasons win percentage and post season wins. We did this by constructing a scatterplot of payroll vs regular season wins, and then we overlaid a linear best-fit line to view the overall trend.

Figure 33: Postseason wins vs payroll

There is a relationship between payroll and getting into the playoffs, but it's not as strong a correlation as one might expect. If we eliminate teams who did not make the postseason, we can test whether spending a lot of money on payroll translates to success in the playoffs:

Figure 34: Postseason wins vs payroll, playoff teams only

To our surprise, we found that there is no statistically significant relationship between winning in the playoffs and payroll. In other words, you may be able to spend money to get into the playoffs, but it does not help at all once you're in. So then, if playoff wins and salary are not correlated, then why are players paid more? To answer this question, we did an analysis of six high salaried players whose pay fell into the outlier category.

Figure 35: High Salary Players Performance

We found that all the six players Jeter, Rodriguez, Kemp, Mauer, Teixeira, and Votto, had outstanding performance metrics with an average Hits of 150, home runs at 22, and RBI at 81 with an average salary of 22 million. This shows that players consistent performance makes them an expensive lot. Among the six players, we found a lot of interesting variations as shown in figure above. Jeter was a great hitter, Rodriguez had the maximum home runs and Mauer had the most RBI.

3.4 Long term player performance

We studied players long-term performance over five seasons to see if the highly paid players consistently

performed well and whether they were justified a higher pay. We compared a players performance in the first two seasons with the last two seasons.

Figure 36: Batters performance (first two seasons)

Figure 37: Batters Performance (last two seasons)

RBI, home runs, and hits in the last seasons tend to decrease, although the batter's salary increases. They perform well for the first two seasons, get a larger contract, and then fail to live up to their earlier numbers.

Similar to batters, the pitchers salary in the preceding seasons had a stronger correlation with wins, strikeouts and ERA than in the following seasons.

Figure 38: Pitchers performance (first two seasons)

In fact, wins, which were the most highly correlated metric of 0.49 in the preceding season, drop to 0.02 in the following two seasons.

Figure 39: Pitchers performance (last two seasons)

Teams should not sign players who are coming off multiple good years; instead, they should try to find players who are the verge of a breakout season. This is what the Oakland A's did in the early 2000s where they were able to compete and beat teams with much greater salaries. They did it by focusing on recruiting undervalued players with high OBP (on-base percentage) and SLG (slugging percentage) but relatively low batting average.

OBP measures how often a batter reaches base for reasons other than fielding error, dropped/uncaught third strike, fielder's obstruction or catcher's interference.

Figure 40: OBP Vs SLG with Salary (\$M) as hue

SLG measures the power of the hitter.

Figure 41: OBP Vs SLG with Batting Average as hue

The scatter plots above show that there are quite a few undervalued players available for a lesser price.

3.5 Career visualization

One idea we had was to come up with a way to visualize a player's entire career longitudinally in one graph. We came up with this. The height of the bars are plate appearances (PA). A full-time player should have at least 500 PA per year. The orange line is OPS (on-base plus slugging) which is a typical single-number measure of a player's hitting ability. The gray line is league average OPS. Stars indicate all-star selections. "MVP" indicates MVP awards. Here's the graph of Mariners, Rangers, and Yankees star Alex Rodriguez:

Here's a player whose career was cut short due to injuries, Red Sox shortstop Nomar Garciaparra. He was never quite the same player after his wrist surgery in 2001, and you can tell from the graph:

Looking at these graphs side by side lets us compare player's careers. Here are two players who had a similar start to their careers, but diverged around the twelve-year mark. Griffey's bars are shorter at around the 2001 season; this is due to injuries. Meanwhile Bonds went on a historic tear, winning four straight MVP awards.

We decided to add a few extra features. For example, team highlighting. Here's a graph of former Pirates, Cubs, and Brewers third baseman Aramis Ramirez, with the Cubs years highlighted in blue.

Graphing a pitcher is different, since they don't use the same statistics. To measure quantity of production, we used innings pitched, and for quality, we used WHIP. Lower is better for that measure. Also we plotted Cy Young awards

instead of MVPs. Here's a pitcher who had a shaky start to his career, but became dominant later.

Instead of OPS, we use walks plus hits per inning pitched (WHIP). Here, a lower number is better. To test this, we graphed Pedro Martinez, who had a few of the all-time great pitching seasons in the late 90's – early 00's:

We also graphed some average pitchers, just to get a sense of what a typical career looked like.

For mapping teammates, we added an option to freeze the horizontal axis, so the years would line up – here's the vaunted 2005 White Sox pitching staff:

Going back to the batting graph. If we add salary, we can see that players are low-paid for their first few years, but then their salary increases due to free agency. In some cases, salary increases dramatically. For example, 3-time MVP Albert Pujols signed a free agent deal to move from the Cardinals to the Angels. His production has declined, but his salary has increased drastically. (Cardinals years in red)

It turns out this is common. Players spend the first few years of their career, after their team scouts them and drafts them, under “rookie” contracts which are usually favorable to the team. After a few good years, they are able to sign free agent contracts for a lot more money.

Note the drastic jump in salary after Adrian Gonzalez’s 2011 season, when he was given a massive contract extension by Boston. His production has declined, and he’s no longer a perennial All-Star, but he’s gotten much more expensive.

The first few years of a player’s career are cost-controlled. Players will be on “rookie” salary deals until they become eligible for free agency. Notice the drastic jumps in salary for these players, and in some cases the precipitous decline in productivity:

Rather than looking at individual players, if we break down player production by age, we can see that the mode age for major league players is 27. Productivity does not vary much by age. In fact most players decline, and the overall numbers are only steady because of survivorship bias (only the great players survive in the majors into their 30s, and their numbers often regress to the average.)

Figure 42: Batting by age

Figure 43: Pitching by age

But if you look at salary by age, the average salary goes up dramatically, especially past age 30, with a slight dip around age 38.

Figure 44: Salary by age

3.6 Team visualization

The next thing we wanted to look at was a team's overall roster. To do this, we started with a scatter plot of the entire league. We made two: one for batting, one for pitching. In the player bar graphs, we had used OPS as the overall quality statistic. Recall that OPS equals on base percentage plus slugging percentage. Here, we are going to break down that number into its two components, OBP% and SLG%.

Figure 45: On base vs slugging

The best players on the chart would be in the top right. There is a rough correlation between the two numbers. The two numbers are intended to measure two different types of skills. OBP% equals hits plus walks divided by plate appearances, and it measures ability to hit for contact. SLG% is total bases divided by at bats, and it measures hitting for power. The best players can do both things well, but there are many specialist players who are better at one or the other. The size of the circle is the number of at bats. Better players tend to get more at bats.

Pitching looks quite a bit different. To map pitchers, we plotted walk rate (walks divided by outs) against hit rate (hits divided by outs). The size is outs pitched. Here, it's better to be in the lower left. In this case, there is very little correlation between the two measures, and players with good numbers may have less playing time; many of them are relief pitchers.

Figure 46: Walk rate vs hit rate

To look at teams, we took these graphs, and overlaid a team's players on top. Because of occlusion, we used alpha to blend them with the chart. Here's the 2017 Angels:

Figure 47: 2017 Angels

The red bubble at the top right is Mike Trout, who is by far the best Angels player. He is also the highest paid, and his salary has made it difficult for the Angels to obtain other players. The 2017 Angels were not a successful team; they had an 80-82 record and missed the playoffs. Contrast this to the 2017 Astros, who won 101 games and were World Series champions:

Figure 48: 2017 Astros

Or the 2016 Cubs (also World Series champions):

Figure 49: 2016 Cubs

These teams have a balance of players in the upper part of the graph – not necessarily at the extreme though. Having a single superstar hitter does not appear to help much, unless they can build a team around him.

For an example of a team that won primarily with pitching, here is the 2005 White Sox staff. Rather than relying on one ace, the team had five above-average starters.

Figure 50: 2005 White Sox pitching

As with the player graph, it's illuminating to add a way to visualize salary. If we look at the very highly paid players – the top 25 salaries for position players – and plot them on a chart against every major league regular, the highly paid cohort doesn't look very different. In fact they are very similar.

Figure 51: 25 highest paid vs everyone else

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Team salary comparisons

To really understand how teams spend their money, we built some charts examining overall payroll and team structure. We went back to the earlier chart, where we plotted team payrolls year-over-year, and added lines to look at certain teams. First we looked at the three biggest spenders: the Yankees (NYA), Dodgers (LAN), and Red Sox (BOS).

Figure 52: Big-spending teams

What's immediately obvious about this chart is that the Yankees – by far the most valuable team – are by far the biggest spenders too, and that they “broke the curve” during the early 00's. They spend much of the decade spending drastically more than everyone else, and it was only recently in 2014 that anyone caught up to them. All that spending post-2000 only netted one World Series win in 2009, so where did the money go? To answer this question, we looked at the highest-paid Yankees over this span:

Figure 53: 12 highest-paid Yankees

Here's a graph of the 12 highest paid Yankees during that time period. That extra spending went mostly to two places: raises to keep their existing players past their rookie deals (Rivera, Jeter, and Posada), and free agent signings (Giambi, Mussina, Sheffield, Clemens). For example Derek Jeter's dark green slice of the graph went from being a tiny sliver in 1996 to a huge chunk by 2006. Let's look at Jeter's career graph:

Or their big free-agent splash of 2002, former Oakland A's slugger Jason Giambi (Yankees years in blue):

Neither player got better. They both just got a lot more expensive.

By way of contrast, this is a the same graph from before, but with the other recent successful teams highlighted. The Cardinals (SLN), World Series winners in 2006 and 2011, the Giants (SFN), winners in 2010, 2012, and 2014, and the Royals (KCA), winners in 2015:

Figure 54: St Louis, SF, and KC payrolls

None of these teams bought their way to success. In fact the the Giant's big recent payroll increase has had diminishing returns (last place in 2018). For an example of a team that was successful in balancing their spending, we can look at the 2016 Cubs. Here is what their overall payroll looked like:

Figure 55: 2016 Cubs payroll

The core of their offense was four players – Kris Bryant, Anthony Rizzo, Javier Baez, and Addison Russell. The total salary of those four players was \$6,976,714, which is less than five percent of the team's total payroll of approximately \$154 million. However, they accounted for nearly half of the team's total offensive production:

Figure 56: 2016 Cubs salary vs offense

4.2 Team continuity

Another angle we wanted to examine was the effect of team continuity. Convention wisdom states that the best teams are cohesive units that stick together and learn to play well as a team. To examine this idea, we developed a type of chart that displays changes in a team's roster over time. Here's an example for the 1996-2000 Yankees:

Figure 57: Yankees team continuity

The rows of the chart are players; the columns are years. The size of each box is number of innings pitched for pitchers, or at bats for position players. A large box is an everyday player, a smaller box is a reserve or a reliever. The color indicates team; in this example the dark blue squares are Yankees seasons, and the grays are seasons played with other teams. For example, Andy Pettitte spent three seasons in Houston. Finally, the yellow highlight bars indicate World Series championship years.

One can see from the chart that this was a team that largely stayed intact. They were able to afford their key players after their rookie deals expired, due to their financial resources. Having built this visualization type, we then went on to look at other successful teams to see how they fared. Here's the Cardinals of the mid-00's:

Figure 58: Cardinals team continuity

The Cardinals, as we saw in a previous graph, are a small-market, medium-payroll team. Yet they were able to keep a successful team intact without breaking the bank.

A classic example of a team **not** being able to stay together is the Oakland A’s of the 1970s:

Figure 59: Athletics team continuity

As you can see, the core of the team that won three straight World Series was entirely gone four years later. This was due to the introduction of free agency in 1976.

It’s still possible to win even without continuity. The Marlins of 1997-2003 are an infamous example. They won the Series twice in six years, with almost completely different rosters:

Figure 60: Marlins team continuity

The “fire sale” Marlins of 1998 lost many of their most important players – Conine, Johnson, Sheffield, Brown, and Leiter, for example – but were able to build a contender again very quickly. (Then they dismantled *that* team a few years later, but that’s another story.)

For a more recent example, this is the 2016 Cubs. They were a team used its resources to build a roster of cost-controlled young players. By doing this they were able to win

the World Series with a team they had assembled in only a few years:

Figure 61: Cubs team continuity

Their success came from a combination of good drafting and scouting, with a few smart free agent acquisitions.

5. Conclusions

The financial system of baseball is unbalanced. Due to the lack of a salary cap, certain teams like the Yankees and Dodgers have revenue and market-size advantages that other teams don’t have. They can spend much higher amounts of money on payroll than other teams. Despite this, it is still possible for lower-revenue teams to win, if they are smart.

Players who have been league longer tend to make more money. Good players will generally get a large pay raise at the time of their first free-agency deal, but this does not often mean a large increase in their quality of play. Most players, in fact, decline as they get older. For this reason, teams should be wary of spending lots of money on big-ticket free agents, and that includes giving raises to retain their own players. Neither is necessary to win.

Teams should avoid wasteful spending. The teams without the deep pockets of the big-market teams can win by stocking their rosters with younger players. This means making a big investment in the scouting and farm systems to obtain these players.

6. Possible future work

In preparing this document, there were many avenues that we wanted to explore but fell outside of the scope of the project. Some of these include:

- Exploring the effectiveness of baseball’s “advanced” stats. Here we used OPS as a shorthand measure for a player’s skill but it would be interesting to look at wins above replacement, OPS+, equivalent average, or other more analytically-derived statistics.

- Looking at the effect of trades, and other types of transactions.
 - A visual analysis of fielding. This is an important part of baseball, but also one that is notoriously difficult to evaluate with statistics. A visual approach might be more suitable.
 - A deeper dive into skills that are valuable to a team versus skills that the market pays for. For example at the time of writing [Moneyball](#), the most “undervalued” skill was on-base percentage. Since then, the economics and spending strategies of the game have shifted, and it would be interesting to visualize how.
 - Somehow combining the year-over-year “team continuity” chart with the stacked graph of team payroll would give a more complete view of a team’s construction, but it might be difficult to combine so many dimensions in one chart.
 - Looking at team contribution as it relates to in-game strategy. Does it matter if a team has an elite leadoff hitter? What are the best ways to deploy relief pitchers? To examine this we’d need an expanded data set with play-by-play of individual games.
 - Comparison of the American League and the National League. Aside from the designated hitter, what are the differences between the two leagues?
 - How does ballpark dimensions influence player performance? For example, Fenway Park in Boston has radically different dimensions than every other ballpark; among many other oddities, there’s a 37-foot wall in left field. Other park effects to consider might include elevation and climate.
 - Do players need to optimize their playing techniques to get maximum impact for their talent they possess?
 - Does weather impact team performance or provide a home-field advantage? 40-degree difference in temperatures between LA and Boston can have an impact during the playoffs.
- www.forbes.com/sites/mikeozanian/2018/04/11/baseball-team-values-2018/.
- [3] Brown, Maury. “MLB's Billion Dollar TV Deals, Free Agency, And Why Robinson Cano's Deal With The Mariners Isn't ‘Crazy.’” *Forbes*, *Forbes Magazine*, 7 Jan. 2014, www.forbes.com/sites/maurybrown/2014/01/07/mlbs-billion-dollar-tv-deals-free-agency-and-why-robinson-canos-deal-with-the-mariners-isnt-crazy/
- [4] Giratikanon, Tom, Katz, Josh, and Quealy, Kevin. “A Map of Baseball Nation.” *The New York Times*, *The New York Times*, 24 Apr. 2014, www.nytimes.com/interactive/2014/04/24/upshot/facebook-baseball-map.html
- [5] Bump, Philip. “Thae Reddest Baseball Fan Base? By Our Estimate, It's the Reds.” *The Washington Post*, WP Company, 29 Mar. 2018, www.washingtonpost.com/news/politics/wp/2018/03/29/the-reddest-baseball-fanbase-by-our-estimate-its-the-reds/?utm_term=.71e8c849558a.
- [6] “Texas Rangers vs Oakland Athletics.” *Major League Baseball*. NBCSports Bay Area.
- [7] “2014 National League Division Series.” *Fox Major League Baseball*. Fox Sports 1.
- [8] “Baseball's Many Dimensions24x18 (2014).” THIRTY81 Project, thirty81project.com/collections/thirty81-collection/products/baseball-s-many-physical-dimensions-poster.
- [9] Robinson, Craig. *Flip Flop Fly Ball*, 1 Nov. 2016, www.flipflopflyin.com/flipflopflyball/info-bestrecord.html.
- [10] “MLB Stats, Scores, History, & Records.” BR Bullpen, www.baseball-reference.com/.
- [11] Visuals, Playbook. “Infographic: Retired Numbers in Baseball.” *ESPN*, *ESPN Internet Ventures*, 13 July 2012, www.espn.com/blog/playbook/visuals/post/_id/5727/infographic-retired-numbers-in-baseball.
- [12] Robinson, Craig. *Flip Flop Fly Ball*, 1 Nov 2016, <http://www.flipflopflyin.com/flipflopflyball/info-postseasonschedule.html>
- [13] Berg, Erik. “Division Race Charts.” *MLB Division Race Charts - Xmlstats*, erikberg.com/mlb/charts.
- [14] Samantha Attar, Hannah Dineen, Andy Fullerton, Nora Hanson, Cam Kelso, Katie McLaughlin, Caitlyn Noah. “Baseball Eras.” <http://web.colby.edu/baseball/files/2016/0>

7. Acknowledgements

This project would not have been possible without the database provided by Sean Lahman.

Team logos from <http://www.sportslogos.net>.

8. References

- [1] Lahman, Sean. “Download Lahman's Baseball Database.” *SeanLahman.com*, www.seanlahman.com/baseball-archive/statistics/.
- [2] Ozanian, Mike. “Baseball Team Values 2018.” *Forbes*, *Forbes Magazine*, 11 Apr. 2018,